

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING, DATA SHARING AND DISTRIBUTED COLLABORATION MAY BE OUR BEST TOOLS TO STUDY THE NEURONAL BASES OF AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER

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Other studies involved the **cerebellum**, which would have a different volume in people with autism compared to unaffected controls: some studies described abnormally small volumes, others abnormally large volumes. Again, these findings could be related to various aspects of autistic behaviour, such as problems with fine motor skills or language.

$\sigma \sim 1 \text{ cm}^2$

Surface area of the human corpus callosum (cm²)

$N=500$

$N=130$

$N=35$

Lefebvre et al. (2015) “Neuroanatomical diversity of corpus callosum...”

Table 3. Meta-analysis: Mean CC Size, Effect Size, Significance of the Difference, Statistical Power.

Reference	N_{ASD}	N_{Ctrl}	Mean $CC_{ASD} \pm SD$ (cm ²)	Mean $CC_{Ctrl} \pm SD$ (cm ²)	Effect Size	p Value (Two-Sided)	Power to Detect SD = .3 (Two-Sided)
Gaffney <i>et al.</i> 1987 (36)	13	35	5.89 ± 1.04	6.24 ± 1.37	-.27	.41	17.3%
Egaas <i>et al.</i> 1995 (37)	51	51	5.57 ± .99	5.89 ± .91	-.33	.097	32.3%
Piven <i>et al.</i> 1997 (38)	35	36	6.15 ± .83	6.40 ± .38	-.39	.11	24.1%
Manes <i>et al.</i> 1999 (39)	27	17	4.64 ± .99	5.71 ± .97	-1.07	.0011	16.2%
Elia <i>et al.</i> 2000 (40)	22	11	5.26 ± 1.00	5.41 ± .64	-.16	.67	12.7%
Rice <i>et al.</i> 2005 (41)	12	8	7.34 ± 1.11	7.75 ± 1.14	-.35	.45	9.3%
Vidal <i>et al.</i> 2006 (42)	24	26	6.06 ± 1.15	6.68 ± .79	-.62	.033	17.9%
Boger-Megiddo <i>et al.</i> 2006 (43)	45	26	4.59 ± .67	4.99 ± .72	-.57	.022	24.1%
Alexander <i>et al.</i> 2007 (44)	43	34	7.87 ± 1.99	9.32 ± .70	-.77	.012	25.2%
Just <i>et al.</i> 2007 (3)	18	18	6.40 ± .88	7.1 ± .88	-.78	.025	13.9%
Hardan <i>et al.</i> 2009 (45)	22	23	5.74 ± 1.13	6.58 ± 1.04	-.76	.014	16.2%
Freitag <i>et al.</i> 2009 (46)	15	15	6.22 ± .45	6.54 ± 1.24	-.34	.36	12.2%
Keary <i>et al.</i> 2009 (47)	32	34	6.19 ± 1.09	6.76 ± 1.10	-.51	.040	22.4%
Anderson <i>et al.</i> 2011 (48)	53	39	6.54 ± 1.20	7.05 ± .90	-.46	.031	29.6%
Hong <i>et al.</i> 2011 (49)	18	16	8.14 ± 1.31	8.27 ± 1.27	-.10	.78	13.3%
Frazier <i>et al.</i> 2012 (50)	23	2	6.30 ± 1.11	6.78 ± 1.08	-.43	.15	16.7%
Prigge <i>et al.</i> 2013 (51)	68	47	5.74 ± .91	6.24 ± .89	-.55	.0044	36.0%

Lefebvre et al. (2015) “Neuroanatomical diversity of corpus callosum...”

Traut et al. (2018) “Cerebellar volume in Autism...”

Table 2. Studies Included in Meta-analysis

Study	N_{ASD} (F)	N_{Ctrl} (F)	Age _{ASD} , Years	Age _{Ctrl} , Years	IQ _{ASD}	IQ _{Ctrl}	Regions of Interest
Hodge <i>et al.</i> , 2010 (30)	22 (0)	11 (0)	9.4 ± 2.0	10.4 ± 2.7	87 ± 22	114 ± 11	Cb, WM, GM, vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Scott <i>et al.</i> , 2009 (31)	48 (0)	14 (0)	12.4 ± 3.1	12.5 ± 3.1	79 ± 23	113 ± 12	Cb, vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Hallahan <i>et al.</i> , 2009 (32)	114 (18)	60 (7)	31.9 ± 10.1	32.0 ± 9.0	97 ± 18	114 ± 12	Cb
Webb <i>et al.</i> , 2009 (33)	45 (7)	26 (8)	3.9 ± 0.3	3.9 ± 0.5	59 ± 21	115 ± 15 ^a	Cb, vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Langen <i>et al.</i> , 2009 (26)	99 (8)	89 (7)	12.9 ± 4.5	12.4 ± 4.8	108 ± 14	110 ± 13	Cb
Lahuis <i>et al.</i> , 2008 (34)	21 (0)	21 (0)	11.1 ± 2.2	10.4 ± 1.8	107 ± 14	103 ± 15	Cb
Cleavinger <i>et al.</i> , 2008 (35)	28 (0)	16 (0)	13.9 ± 5.3	13.9 ± 5.4	99 ± 18	102 ± 14	Cb, WM, GM, vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Catani <i>et al.</i> , 2008 (36)	15 (0)	16 (0)	31.0 ± 9.0	35.0 ± 11.0	109 ± 17	120 ± 21	Cb
Bloss and Courchesne, 2007 (37)	9 (9)	14 (14)	3.7 ± 0.9	3.8 ± 1.1	83 ± 18	119 ± 13	Cb, WM, GM
Hazlett <i>et al.</i> , 2005 (38)	51 (5)	14 (4)	2.7 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.4	54 ± 9	108 ± 19	Cb, WM, GM
Palmen <i>et al.</i> , 2004 (39)	21 (2)	21 (1)	20.1 ± 3.1	20.3 ± 2.2	115 ± 19	113 ± 10	Cb
Kates <i>et al.</i> , 2004 (40)	9 (1)	16 (2)	7.6 ± 2.4	8.3 ± 2.4	70 ± 19	124 ± 10	Cb, WM, GM
Akshoomoff <i>et al.</i> , 2004 (41)	52 (0)	15 (0)	3.8 ± 0.8	3.6 ± 1.1	82 ± 24	108 ± 18 ^b	I–V, VI–VII
Herbert <i>et al.</i> , 2003 (42)	17 (0)	15 (0)	9.0 ^b ± 1.4 ^b	9.0 ^b ± 1.4 ^b	100 ± 15 ^c	115 ± 15 ^a	Cb
Kaufmann <i>et al.</i> , 2003 (43)	10 (0)	22 (0)	6.9 ± 2.4	8.3 ± 1.9	66 ± 14	121 ± 9	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Pierce and Courchesne, 2001 (44)	14 (2)	14 (4)	3.8 ± 1.1	4.4 ± 1.2	84 ± 24	110 ± 12	I–V, VI–VII
Courchesne <i>et al.</i> , 2001 (45)	60 (0)	52 (0)	6.2 ± 3.5	8.1 ± 3.5	79 ± 26	115 ^b ± 15 ^b	Cb, WM, GM
Hardan <i>et al.</i> , 2001 (46)	22 (0) ^d	22 (0) ^d	22.4 ± 10.1	22.4 ± 10.0	100 ± 15	100 ± 14	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X, Cb
Elia <i>et al.</i> , 2000 (47)	22 (0)	11 (0)	10.9 ± 4.0	10.9 ± 2.9	55 ± 10 ^e	115 ± 15 ^a	Vermis, VI–VII
Carper and Courchesne, 2000 (48)	42 (0)	29 (0)	5.4 ± 1.7	6.0 ± 1.8	80 ± 22	114 ± 12	VI–VII
Levitt <i>et al.</i> , 1999 (49)	8 (NR)	21 (NR)	12.5 ± 2.2	12.0 ± 2.8	83 ± 12	115 ± 11	VIII–X
Piven <i>et al.</i> , 1997 (50)	35 (9)	36 (16)	18.0 ± 4.5	20.2 ± 3.8	91 ± 20	102 ± 13	Cb
Ciesielski <i>et al.</i> , 1997 (51)	9 (4)	10 (3)	16.8 ± 5.2 ^b	16.6 ± 5.4 ^b	93 ^b ± 13 ^b	119 ^b ± 10 ^b	I–V, VI–VII
Hashimoto <i>et al.</i> , 1995 (52)	96 (24)	112 (47)	6.4 ± 4.9	7.2 ± 5.2	60 ± 25	99 ± 18	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Courchesne <i>et al.</i> , 1994 (53)	50 (9)	53 (10)	16.5 ± 11.6 ^b	18.8 ± 10.4 ^b	81 ^b ± 31 ^b	115 ± 15 ^a	I–V, VI–VII
Piven <i>et al.</i> , 1992 (54)	15 (0)	15 (0)	27.7 ± 10.7	28.8 ± 5.6	92 ± 23	130 ± 0	I–V, VI–VII
Holttum <i>et al.</i> , 1992 (55)	18 (0)	18 (0)	20.2 ± 8.1	20.2 ± 8.3	94 ± 12	95 ± 12	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII, VIII–X
Garber and Ritvo, 1992 (56)	12 (3)	12 (4)	27.2 ± 5.3	26.4 ± 3.6	95 ± 15 ^f	115 ± 15 ^a	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII
Kleiman <i>et al.</i> , 1992 (57)	13 (3)	17 (8)	7.7 ± 5.7	7.0 ± 4.3 ^b	52 ± 17	115 ± 15 ^a	I–V, VI–VII
Ritvo <i>et al.</i> , 1988 (58)	15 (4)	15 (4)	11.6 ± 4.1	11.6 ± 4.1	75 ± 15	115 ± 15 ^a	Vermis, I–V, VI–VII

Traut et al. (2018) "Cerebellar volume in Autism..."

Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange I ABIDE I

The Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange I (ABIDE I) represents the first ABIDE initiative. Started as a grass roots effort, ABIDE I involved 17 international sites, sharing previously collected resting state functional magnetic resonance imaging (R-fMRI), anatomical and phenotypic datasets made available for data sharing with the broader scientific community. This effort yielded 1112 dataset, including 539 from individuals with ASD and 573 from typical controls (ages 7-64 years, median 14.7 years across groups). This aggregate was released in August 2012. Its establishment demonstrated the feasibility of aggregating resting state fMRI and structural MRI data across sites; the rate of these data use and resulting publications (see [Manuscripts](#)) have shown its utility for capturing whole brain and regional properties of the brain connectome in Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). In accordance with HIPAA guidelines and 1000 Functional Connectomes Project / INDI protocols, all datasets have been anonymized, with no protected health information included. Below, are the specific types of information included in ABIDE I, the data usage agreement, sign up and data download links.

Last Updated June 24, 2016.

ABIDE I Credits

Consortium Founders

[Adriana Di Martino](#)^{1,5}, [Stewart Mostofsky](#)²

Project Coordinator

Adriana Di Martino^{1,5}

Phenotypic Data Aggregation and Organization

Adriana Di Martino^{1,5}, Erin Denio¹, Michael P. Milham^{3,4}

Imaging Data Aggregation and Organization

The INDI Team:

Qingyang Li³, Ranjit Khanuja³, Sharad Sikka^{1,4},
Chao-Gan Yan⁴, Cameron Craddock³, [Michael P. Milham](#)^{3,4}

Website Design

Brett Lullo¹, Adriana Di Martino^{1,5}

Website Updates

David O'Connor³, Andrea Devoto¹

Additional Website Support

Daniel Lurie³, Anna Rachlin³, Emily Brady¹

ABIDE Design Element

Dawn Thomsen³, Nancy Duan³, Adriana Di Martino^{1,5}

Special thanks to F. Xavier Castellanos^{1,4} for his advisory role and naming of the ABIDE consortium, as well as his continued support for FCP/INDI efforts.

- Affiliation at ABIDE I Release: Phyllis Green and Randolph Cowen Institute for Pediatric Neuroscience at the NYU Child Study Center, New York University Langone Medical Center, New York, New York, United States of America.
- Laboratory for Neurocognitive and Imaging Research, Kennedy Krieger Institute, Baltimore, Maryland, United States of America.
- Center for the Developing Brain, Child Mind Institute, New York, New York, United States of America.
- Nathan S. Kline Institute for Psychiatric Research, Orangeburg, New York, United States of America.
- Current affiliation: Autism Center at the Child Mind Institute, New York, New York, United States of America.

Usage Agreement

Consistent with the policies of the 1000 Functional Connectomes Project, data usage is unrestricted for non-commercial research purposes. We kindly request that the specific datasets included in analyses be specified appropriately, and that their funding sources be acknowledged. As per INDI protocol, we simply require that users register with the NITRC and 1000 Functional Connectomes Project to gain access. ([Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-Share Alike License](#))

Note: In order to access ABIDE datasets, users must be logged into NITRC at the time of download and registered with the 1000 Functional Connectomes Project / INDI website. A permission error message will occur if you are not logged in and properly registered.

[Register for NITRC and INDI](#)

ABIDE I Downloads

Phenotypic data

ABIDE I Sites

California Institute of Technology

Carnegie Mellon University

Kennedy Krieger Institute

Ludwig Maximilians University Munich

NYU Langone Medical Center

Olin, Institute of Living at Hartford Hospital

Oregon Health and Science University

San Diego State University

Social Brain Lab BCN NIC UMC Groningen and Netherlands Institute for Neurosciences

Stanford University

Trinity Centre for Health Sciences

University of California, Los Angeles: Sample 1

University of California, Los Angeles: Sample 2

University of Leuven: Sample 1

University of Leuven: Sample 2

Autism Brain Imaging Data Exchange II ABIDE II

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Last Updated March 27, 2017.

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Project Directors

[Adriana Di Martino](#)^{1,4}, [Michael P. Milham](#)^{2,3}

Coordination

Adriana Di Martino^{1,4}

Phenotypic Data Aggregation and Organization

Bosi Chen¹, Tanmay Nath¹, Adriana Di Martino^{1,4}

Imaging Data Aggregation and Organization

David O'Connor^{2,3}, Michael P. Milham^{2,3}
* Additional support provided by Lindsay Alexander^{2,3}, Yuta Aoki¹, Cameron Craddock^{2,3}, Dorothea Floris¹, Erica Ho^{2,3} and Tanmay Nath¹

Website Organization

Tanmay Nath¹, Bosi Chen¹, Adriana Di Martino^{1,4}, Michael P. Milham^{2,3}

- Affiliation at ABIDE II Release: [Autism Spectrum Disorder Research and Clinical Program](#) at the Child Study Center, New York University Langone Medical Center, New York, New York, United States of America.
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ABIDE II Release Updates

[Release update - 3/27/2017](#)

[Release update - 9/25/2016](#)

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Phenotypic data

- [ABIDE II Composite Phenotypic File](#)
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- [ABIDE II Phenotypic Data Legend](#)

Imaging data

- [ABIDE II MRI Data Quality Metrics](#)

See individual site profiles to the right for MRI protocol information and imaging files available for download.

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ABIDE II Collections

Barrow Neurological Institute

Erasmus University Medical Center Rotterdam

ETH Zürich

Georgetown University

Indiana University

Institut Pasteur and Robert Debré Hospital

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven

Kennedy Krieger Institute

NYU Langone Medical Center: Sample 1

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N=2226

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- Coordination**
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 - Michael P. Milham^{2,3}
 - Tammy Chen¹, Tanmay Nath¹, Ashwini Anand¹, Adriana Di Martino^{1,4}
 - Imaging Data Aggregation and Organization
 - David O'Connor^{2,3}, Michael P. Milham^{2,3}
 - * Additional support provided by Lindsay A. Glaser¹, Yuta Aoki¹, Cameron Craddock^{2,3}, Patricia Floris¹, Erin Denio¹, Chao-Gan Yan⁴, and Tanmay Nath¹
 - Website Design
 - Tammy Nath¹, Bosi Chen¹, Adriana Di Martino^{1,4}, Michael P. Milham^{2,3}

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- ETH Zürich
- Georgetown University
- Indiana University
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- Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
- Kennedy Krieger Institute
- NYU Langone Medical Center: Sample 1
- NYU Langone Medical Center: Sample 2
- Olin Neuropsychiatry Research Center, Institute of Living at Hartford Hospital
- Oregon Health and Science University
- Trinity Centre for Health Sciences
- San Diego State University
- Stanford University

A vast desert landscape with rolling sand dunes under a clear blue sky. The dunes are golden-brown and have soft, undulating shapes. The sky is a uniform, clear blue. The overall scene is serene and empty.

[we found nothing...]

Wow.

Wow.

Is MRI even relevant for the exploration of neurodevelopmental disorders?

There were some things we did find:

Large brains have a **proportionally smaller** corpus callosum than average size brains

There were some things we did find:

The correlation between brain volume and IQ is **weaker among patients**

(controls: 1 IQ/31 cm³,
ASD: 1 IQ/84 cm³)

There were some things we did find:

“Normalisation”
is **unable to control** for the
non-linear effect
of brain allometry

IQ matching can
induce
artefactual
neuroanatomic
al differences

Instead of keep looking brain region after
brain region, we decided to make our data
open, and engage the whole community to
look into the issue:

IMPAC

IMaging-PsychiAtry Challenge: predicting autism

A data challenge on Autism Spectrum Disorder detection

Deadline: July 1, 2018 - 8 pm (UTC)

-129

Days

20

Hours

11

Minutes

35

Seconds

DISCOVER

What is this challenge?

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a severe psychiatric disorder that affects 1 in 166 children.

There is evidence that ASD is reflected in individuals brain networks and anatomy. Yet, it remains unclear how systematic these effects are, and how large is their predictive remain unclear. The large cohort assembled here can bring some answers. Predicting autism from brain imaging will provide biomarkers and shed some light on the mechanisms of the pathology.

Joining the competition

The goal of the competition is to predict the diagnostic status from brain imaging data in the hidden test set. The data of the test set are on a server, hidden from participants. Prediction is done by submitting Python code that will be first trained by the server on training images, and then applied to predict on the hidden test set.

Prizes

The best performers will be awarded prizes at the end of the competitive period, based on the metrics used during the challenge: 1st - 3000 €, 2nd - 2000 €, 3rd - 1000 €, from 4th to 10th - 500 €.

The timeline

This challenge is made of 2 phases:

1. a **competitive phase** up to July 1 in which participants can submit their solutions to the [RAMP](#) platform. A Q&A session regarding the challenge and technical platform is organized May 14;
2. a **collaborative phase** from July 1 to July 7. This last day will coincide with the awards ceremony.

A big data challenge

Multimodal imaging data

Structural MRI

- Preprocessed with FreeSurfer and FSL
- Gray matter volume, area, and thickness
- Average for each Desikan cortical parcel.

Functional MRI

- Resting state fMRI
- Time series extracted on different atlases

Autism Spectrum Disorder classification, 2018 data challenge

c. Prediction accuracy (AUC=0.76±0.01)

d. Prediction for various sample sizes

OK!

So, what next?

1. Use it as a blackbox to **help diagnosis**

Control

Autistic

Confirmatory threshold

Screening threshold

2. Use it to **understand the causes** of neurodevelopmental disorders

What is in a Magnetic Resonance Image?

MAGNETOM Solo

A BioMatrix System

Credit: Heuer 2019

Credit: Dosenbach et al 2010

biobank^{uk}

biobank^{uk}

N=100,000

To address the challenge of using neuroimaging to understand neurodevelopmental disorders,

We need to develop a **conceptual framework** appropriate for this scale,

With relevant theoretical, statistical and animal models.

2. Cortical surface 3D reconstructions

BrainBox

Real-time collaboration in neuroimaging

BrainBox allows you to visualise, segment and annotate collaboratively any brain MRI dataset available online. Segmentations and annotations are automatically saved. Point BrainBox to your own nii.gz or mgz data online, or participate in the projects created by the community.

Enter the URL of an MRI (.nii.gz or .mgz) and click Go

[A list of brains to try](#)

F17_P32

Name: F17_P32
Data source: https://zenodo.org/record/893587/files/sub-17_age-P32_T2.nii.gz
Inclusion date: 15/12/2017

Volume Annotations				
Name	Value	Project	Modified	Access
Default	Foreground		15/12/2017	

Text Annotations				
Name	Value	Project	Modified	Access
MRI Quality	Empty	FIIND	17/09/2017	
Comments	Empty	FIIND	17/09/2017	

volume: 0 mm3
slice: 60

Sag Cor Axi

Stereographer

localhost/stereographic/

- Open Spherical Mesh
- Open Sulcal Map
- Open Annotation
- Save Annotation
- Export Lines
- Import Lines
- Export Labels
- Open Native Mesh
- Move
- Draw
- Select
- +
-
- Delete
- Rename
- Stereographic
- Orthographic
- Solid
- Wireframe

Foubet et al (Cortex 2019)

P32

P8

To address the challenge of using MRI to understand neurodevelopmental disorders,

We need to develop a **methodological framework** appropriate for this scale,

Building and designing the relevant computational tools and a more collaborative way of working.

b

a. Phenotypic correlations

b. Genetic correlations

Biton et al (Cereb Cortex 2019)

**A standardised
project structure**

**Version control
of code**

**Version control
of data**

**Open source
best practices**

**Continuous integration
of modifications**

Confirmatory Results

Comment on this paper

← Previous

Polygenic architecture of human neuroanatomical diversity

Posted April 05, 2019.

 Roberto Toro

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/592337>

This article is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed [what does this mean?].

 Tweet

 Like 0

New Results

Comment on this paper

← Previous

Evolution of neocortical folding: A phylogenetic comparative analysis of MRI from 34 primate species

Posted April 13, 2019.

Katja Heuer, Omer Faruk Gulban, Pierre-Louis Bazin, Anastasia Osoianu, Romain Valabregue, Mathieu Santin, Marc Herbin, Roberto Toro

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/379750>

Now published in *Cortex* doi: [10.1016/j.cortex.2019.04.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cortex.2019.04.011)

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New Results

Comment on this paper

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Mechanical morphogenesis and the development of neocortical organisation

Posted June 23, 2015.

Ophélie Foubet, Roberto Toro

doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/021311>

This article is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed [what does this mean?].

 Tweet

 Like 0

Subject Area

Neuroscience

Subject Areas

All Articles

Animal Behavior and

Abstract Full Text Info/History Metrics Preview PDF

Abstract

The development and evolution of complex neocortical organisations is thought to result from the interaction of genetic and activity-dependent processes. Here we propose that a third type of process – mechanical morphogenesis – may also play an important role. We review recent theoretical and experimental results in non-linear physics showing how homogeneous growth can produce a rich variety of forms, in particular neocortical folding. The mechanical

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Genomic architecture of neuroanatomical diversity

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A comparison between diffusion tractography and tract tracing in ferrets

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Data Challenge on Autism Spectrum Disorder detection <https://paris-saclay-cds.github.io/au...>

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neuroanatomy / **BrainBox**

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BrainBox is a web application that let's you annotate and segment 3D brain imaging data in real time, collabora
<http://brainbox.pasteur.fr>

Manage topics

1,297 commits 4 branches 0 releases 19 contributors

Branch: master New pull request Create new file Upload files Find

katjaq Merge pull request #226 from katjaq/master

.circleci	update docker mongo version
autism_starting_kit.ipynb	FIX address joris comments
download_data.py	fix hash file names for download
environment.yml	MAINT update the version of scikit-learn
problem.py	DATA: add repetition time (ramp-kits#39)
requirements.txt	MAINT update the version of scikit-learn

BrainBox

Real-time collaboration in neuroimaging

BrainBox allows you to visualise, segment and annotate collaboratively any brain MRI dataset available online. Segmentations and annotations are automatically saved. Point BrainBox to your own nii.gz or mgz data online, or participate in the projects created by the community.

Enter the URL of an MRI (.nii.gz or .mgz) and click Go

Name Hutchinson Ferret Atlas
Data source https://files.osf.io/v1/resources/3h9gf/providers/osfstorage/591c54529ad5a10251a7e738?direct=true
Inclusion date 17/05/2017

Volume Annotations

Name	Value	Project	Modified	Access
Default	Foreground		17/05/2017	👁️✎️+ -
Hutchinson Atlas	Ferret 50 Regic		17/05/2017	👁️✎️+ -
Hutchinson Atlas v2	Ferret 50 Regic		17/05/2017	👁️✎️+ -
Regions	10 regions	ferret	08/06/2017	👁️✎️+ -

Text Annotations

Name	Value	Project	Modified	Access
Comments	undefined	ferret	05/12/2017	👁️✎️+ -
Data quality	undefined	ferret	05/12/2017	👁️✎️+ -

volume: 6684 mm3
 slice: 76

Sag Cor Axi

 1 2 3 5 10 15

Chat (1 connected)

MicroDraw

Collaborative atlas creation

MicroDraw is a web application to visualise and annotate collaboratively high resolution histology data. Annotations are vectorial, and you can use boolean operations to combine, subtract and split regions. Point MicroDraw to your own DeepZoom data, or try the sample datasets below.

Enter a DeepZoom image URL and click Go

[A list of datasets to try](#) [Go](#)

The interface displays a histology image of a brain section. A 5 mm scale bar is visible in the top right corner. A navigation toolbar on the left includes icons for pan, home, zoom in, zoom out, and a slider set to 29. Below the toolbar are icons for various drawing and editing tools. A 'Regions' panel is visible at the bottom left. A red box highlights a specific region in the top left corner of the image. The 'naat' logo is in the bottom right corner.

MRI is probably our best tool today to study the neuronal bases of ASD

We need to build a large, open, MRI data resource

Use shared data

Share your data

Heterogeneity is good: it helps generalisation

Collaboration among clinicians, neuroscientists and engineers is essential

We need to be part of the international effort

Open science is not just nicer: it discloses a new type of research

We need to make science open by design

@R3RT0

rto@pasteur.fr

Except where otherwise noted, this presentation by Roberto Toro is licensed under <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>